

pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine reacted with ethyl cyanoacetate to give 9,12-dihydro-3-hydroxy-11-methyl-9,12-diphenyl-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-11*

Compd no	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	m/z M ⁺	δ
2a	184	3 310 (NH ₂), 2 210 (CN)	5.4 (1H, s, H-4), 7.2-8.2 (15H, m, ArH)	6.8 (2H, s, NH ₂)
2b	193	3 320 (NH ₂), 2 225 (CN)	5.5 (1H, s, H-4), 7.1-8.2 (14H, m, ArH)	6.9 (2H, s, NH ₂)
2c	226	3 300 (NH ₂), 2 230 (CN)	2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.8 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.1-8.1 (14H, m, ArH)	5.5 (1H, s, H-4)
2d	219	3 300 (NH ₂), 2 220 (CN)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.9 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7-8.2 (14H, m, ArH)	5.5 (1H, s, H-4)
4	204	2 230 (CN)	1.2 (3H, t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 4.5 (2H, q, CH ₂), 5.5 (1H, s, H-4), 7-8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 8.9 (1H, s, CH-OEt)	3.9 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
5	221	3 300-3 1000 (NH ₂ , NH)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.7 (1H, s, NH), 6.8 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.0-8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, H-7)	5.6 (1H, s, H-4)
6	260	2 960 (CH), 1 600 (C=N)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.2-8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 8.8 (1H, s, H-2), 9.0 (1H, s, H-5)	5.8 (1H, s, H-11)
7	264	2 980 (CH), 1 610 (C=N)	2.7 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.8 (1H, s, H-11), 7.3-8.1 (14H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, H-5)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
8	245	2 960 (CH), 1 600 (C=N)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.3-8.1 (19H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, H-5)	5.8 (1H, s, H-11)
9	265	2 960 (CH), 1 610 (C=N)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.3 (1H, br, CH ₂), 5.8 (1H, s, H-11), 7-8.1 (14H, m, ArH)	5.3 (1H, br, CH ₂)
10	263	2 960 (CH), 2 250 (CN)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.9 (1H, s, H-4), 7-8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 8.9 (1H, s, H-5)	5.1 (1H, br, CH ₂)
11	274	1 780 (CO), 1 600 (C=N)	3.9 (3H, s, COOCH ₃), 5.9 (1H, s, H-11), 7.3-8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, H-5)	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

2*H*-pyrazolo[4',3'':5',6']pyrano[2',3':4,5]pyrimido[1,6-*b*]1,2,4-triazine and with ethyl chloroformate through elimination of ethanol to yield 6-chlorocarbonylamino derivative. While in the present work, interaction of compound 5 with ethyl cyanoacetate led to 2-cyanomethyl-8,11-dihydro-11-*p*-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-*e*]1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidine (10).

Moreover, reaction of methyl chloroformate with 5 in dry benzene furnished via cyclisation 3-carbomethoxy-2,3,8-11-tetrahydro-11-*p*-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[2,3-*e*]1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidin-2-one (11).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The microanalyses were performed at Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University. Ir spec-

tra (KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu 440 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a FX 90 Q Fourier transform spectrometer and mass spectra on a HP MS 5988 instrument using direct inlet system.

*6-Amino-5-cyano-1,4-dihydro-4-aryl-1,3-diphenylpyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles (2a-d)*: A mixture of 1,3-diphenylpyrazol-5-one³ (2.36 g, 10 mmol) and 1a-d (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), was treated with a few drops of piperidine. The mixture was refluxed for 1 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-benzene as colourless crystals (82-88%).

*Ethyl N-(5-cyano-1,4-dihydro-4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,3-diphenylpyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-6-yl)methanimidate (4)*: A mixture of 2d (2.1g, 5 mmol), triethyl orthoformate (0.741 g, 5 mmol) and acetic anhydride (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid product was crystallised from benzene as pale yellow crystals (80%).

*6-Amino-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-5-imino-4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,3-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (5)*: To a solution of 4 (2.38 g, 5 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), hydrazine hydrate (100%-2 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene as colourless crystals (78%).

*8,11-Dihydro-11-*p*-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-*e*]1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidine (6)*. *Method (A)*: A mixture of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and formic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The mixture was then diluted with water and the solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid as pale yellow crystals (60%). *Method (B)*: A solution of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and triethyl orthoformate (0.741 g, 5 mmol) in xylene (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The solvent was then concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was crystallised (80%).

*2-Methyl-8,11-dihydro-11-*p*-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-*e*]1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidine (7)*. *Method (A)*: The reaction of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) with glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was carried out as in the reaction of 5 with formic acid. The product was crystallised from acetic acid as pale yellow crystals (52%). *Method (B)*: A mixture of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and acetyl chloride (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid, (58%).

*8,11-Dihydro-11-*p*-methoxyphenyl-2,8,10-triphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-*e*]1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidine (8)*. *Method (A)*: A mixture of 5 (2.31g, 5 mmol) and 1a (0.77 g, 5 mmol) in dioxane (20 ml) and catalytic amount of piperidine was refluxed for 12 h. The mixture was then cooled and the separated solid crystallised from DMF as pale yellow crystals (60%). *Method (B)*: A mixture of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and benzoyl chloride (10 ml)

was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted with cold NaOH solution and the solid obtained was washed with water and crystallised from DMF, (61%). *Method (C)* : A mixture of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and benzaldehyde (0.53 ml, 5 mmol) in dioxane (15 ml) and a catalytic amount of piperidine was refluxed for 12 h. The solid formed was crystallised from DMF.

2-Chloromethyl-8,11-dihydro-11-p-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidine (9) : A mixture of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) and chloroacetyl chloride (1 ml) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling, the solid product was crystallised from ethanol-benzene (73%).

2-Cyanomethyl-8,11-dihydro-11-p-methoxyphenyl-8,10-diphenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidine (10) : A solution of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with ethyl cyanoacetate (0.6 ml, 5 mmol) for 8 h. The mixture was then cooled and the solid obtained crystallised from ethanol-benzene as colourless crystals (63%).

3-Carbomethoxy-2,3,8,11-tetrahydro-11-p-methoxyphenyl-8,10-dephenylpyrazolo[4',3':5,6]pyrano[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-2-one (11) : To a solution of 5 (2.31 g, 5 mmol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added an excess of methyl chloroformate (1.5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 h. After cooling, the solid that

separated was crystallised from ethanol-benzene as white crystals (79%).

References

1. F. FREEMAN, *Chem Rev.*, 1980 **80**, 239; H. A. ELFAHAM, F M ADEL-GALLI, Y. R. IBRAHEIM and M. H. ELNAGDI, *J Heterocycl Chem.*, 1983, **20**, 667; M. H. ELNAGDI, R. M. ABDEL-MOTALEB M. MUSTAFA, M. F. ZAYED and E. M. KAMEL, *J Heterocycl Chem* 1987, **24**, 1677 M. H. ELNAGDI, N. H. TAHA, F. A. ABD EL AIL R. M. ABD-EL-MOTALEB and F. F. MAHAMOUD, *Collect Czech Chem Commun*, 1989 **54** 1082, A. F. HARB, A. B. HUSSEIN, S. A. METWALLY and M. H. ELNAGDI, *Bull Fac Sci, Assiut Univ* 1991, **20**, 135; M. T. COCCO, C. CONGIU, A. MACCINOI and V. ONNIS, *J Heterocycl Chem*, 1993, **30**, 353
2. S. Y. K. TAM, R. S. KLEIN, I. WEMPEN and J. J. FOX, *J Org Chem* 1979, **44**, 4547; S. C. SHARMA and B. M. LYNCH, *Can J Chem* 1979, **57**, 3034; M. H. ELNAGDI, M. R. H. EL-MOGHAYAR D H FLEITA, E. A. HAFEZ and S. M. FAHMY, *J Org Chem.* 1976 **41** 3781, G. W. MILLER and F. L. ROSE, *J Chem Soc*, 1963, 5642, 1965, 3357.
3. L. KNORR and C. KIOTZ, *Chem Ber* 1887 **20**, 2545; P. N. PAHL, T. E. ACHARY and A. J. NAYAK, *J Indian Chem Soc* 1975, **52** 1196.
4. K. C. LIU, B. J. SHIH and J. W. CHERM, *J Heterocycl Chem* 1989, **26**, 457.
5. M. I. YOUNES, S. A. METWALLY and A. H. ATTA, *Synthesis* 1990, 704.